

6-Hydroxyquinolyl-5- β -acrylic Acids (*cis*- and *trans*-) and their Derivatives.

BY BIMAN BIHARI DEY AND TIRUVENKATA RAJENDRA SESHADRI.

Quinolino-6:5-*a*-pyrones (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 187; also *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 116, 531), when freshly precipitated from an acid solution, dissolve in a dilute solution of alkali to a considerable extent in the cold, but when recrystallised are insoluble except on heating. The difference is explained by the fact that a freshly prepared quinolino-pyrone is accompanied by the acid that is formed by the rupture of the pyrone ring: the acid, however, is unstable and changes into the quinolino-pyrone on treatment with a hot solvent.

These acids have now been isolated in the pure condition in the form of pale yellow crystalline powders. They rapidly lose water and form pyrones even at the laboratory temperature: their silver salts can be preserved unchanged for a longer time if kept in desiccators of non-actinic glass. They should obviously be regarded as *cis*-6-hydroxyquinolyl-5- β -acrylic acids. The relation between the quinolino-pyrone and the acrylic acid is shown below:—

The *cis*-isomers being too unstable to work with, attention was directed to the preparation of the *trans*-isomers by the methods generally employed for converting coumarins into coumaric or *trans*-hydroxycinnamic acids, *i.e.*, by heating with concentrated alkali or sodium ethoxide in alcoholic solution for several hours, or by fusion with potash at 250°—300° for a shorter time. These methods, however, did not lead to the desired result, only the unchanged pyrones being obtained at the end of the operation. Coumarin itself yields, under the same conditions, first coumaric and subsequently salicylic acid.

The basic quinoline ring appears, therefore, to confer stability on the pyrone nucleus. Similar observations have been recorded in the case of some amino-coumarins (Pechmann, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 3684) and nitro-coumarins (Dey and Row, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 128, 555) which are unaffected by boiling alkalis or sodium alcoholates, whilst 8-nitro-coumarin provides one of the few instances of a coumarin yielding a stable coumarinic acid. These examples seem to point to the existence of a remarkable influence of either acidic or basic groups in stabilizing the coumarinic, *i.e.*, the *cis*-phase, so that the ordinary methods are of no avail in converting them into the corresponding coumaric or *trans*-acids.

The new method recently developed in this laboratory (*cf.* Dey and Row, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 554) was therefore tried, and it was found that on boiling the quinolino-pyrones successively with sodium sulphite and concentrated alkali solutions, they were completely converted into the salts of the *trans*-acids. The change is represented as taking place in the following way:—

The *trans*-hydroxyquinolyl acrylic acids are stable substances, soluble both in acids and alkalis, but dissolving with great difficulty in the ordinary organic solvents. They are quantitatively transformed into the quinolino-pyrones on warming with concentrated sulphuric acid on the water-bath, and they decompose vigorously at their melting points into carbon dioxide and the corresponding hydroxy-quinolyl-ethylenes. These reactions, which are parallel to the changes undergone by coumaric acid itself under the same conditions, as well as their mode of preparation, furnish definite evidence of the *trans*-structure of the acids. The curious observation, however, was made that the ethyl esters of the *trans*-acids possess the remarkable property, verified in several cases in the course of these investigations, of eliminating alcohol when heated above their melting points and passing into the quinolino-pyrones.

The acids and their esters, therefore, behave differently when heated, the former like other *trans*-acids of this series losing carbon dioxide and passing into styrene derivatives, whilst the latter split off

ethyl alcohol and form quinolino-pyrones, as if they had the *cis*-configuration. The presumption that the acids had undergone a change in configuration during the process of esterification seems to be untenable, because the esters, on keeping in contact with cold alcoholic potash, were found to be hydrolysed to the original *trans*-acids. The various changes are shown in the scheme given below:—

There are many cases on record in which the elimination of atoms or groups takes place very readily from the *trans*-position; thus, the *trans*-forms of β -chlorocrotonic acid, bromo-stilbene and bromobutylene lose halogen acid with ease, although the corresponding *cis*-derivatives do not (*cf.* Frankland, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912. 101, 681).

The hydroxyquinolyl ethylenes are colourless solids, melting at high temperatures; they readily dissolve in dilute caustic soda and in dilute hydrochloric acid to form colourless solutions which soon deposit the sparingly soluble sodium salt or the hydrochloride. Neutral ferric chloride develops a fine pink colour, indicating the presence of a phenolic group.

EXPERIMENTAL.

ACTION OF ALKALI ON QUINOLINO-PYRONES.

cis-6-Hydroxyquinolyl-5- β -acrylic Acid.

General Method.

The quinolino-pyrene (2 g.) was dissolved in boiling 10 per cent. potassium hydroxide (20 c.c.) and the yellow solution cooled in ice and carefully neutralised with *N*-hydrochloric acid, when the

cis-hydroxyquinolyl acrylic acid mixed with some unchanged pyrone was precipitated. The latter was eliminated by treating the product with cold dilute sodium carbonate and neutralising the rapidly filtered solution. On repeating this operation twice, the *cis*-acid was obtained as a yellow micro-crystalline powder, completely soluble in cold dilute sodium carbonate with a deep yellow colour. The acid could not be preserved unchanged for more than a few hours at the ordinary temperature, and after leaving for a day most of it was found to be insoluble in sodium carbonate having changed into the pyrone. The same ring closure also occurred on attempting to crystallise the acid from low boiling solvents like acetone, chloroform or methyl alcohol.

The *di-silver salt* was obtained by the action of silver nitrate on an aqueous solution of the potassium salt. The latter was produced by dissolving a weighed quantity of the quinolino-pyrone in a known excess of dilute potash (over 2 molecules) and subsequently removing the excess by the addition of the calculated quantity of dilute nitric acid. It separates as a deep yellow, flocculent precipitate and when kept dry slowly turned grey on standing; it regenerated the original quinolino-pyrone, when treated with dilute nitric acid or sulphuretted hydrogen.

cis-6-Hydroxyquinolyl-5- β -acrylic Acid.

It was obtained from quinolino-6:5- α -pyrone as a light yellow powder. It underwent rapid decomposition at about 180° and changed into the original pyrone melting at 231-232°. The *silver salt* was analysed. (Found: Ag, 50.2. C₁₁H₇O₂NAg, requires Ag, 50.4 per cent.).

cis-2-Methyl-6-hydroxyquinolyl-5- β -acrylic acid was produced from 2-methylquinolino-6:5- α -pyrone. It decomposed rapidly at about 175° and the product of decomposition was identified with the original pyrone. The *silver salt* was analysed. (Found: Ag, 49.0. C₁₂H₉O₂NAg, requires Ag, 48.7 per cent.).

cis-8-Methyl-6-hydroxyquinolyl-5- β -acrylic acid, the product of hydrolysis of 8-methylquinolino-6:5- α -pyrone, is a bright yellow powder decomposing rapidly at about 120°. The orange coloured *silver salt* was analysed. (Found: Ag, 48.3. C₁₃H₁₁O₂NAg, requires Ag, 48.7 per cent.).

*Action of Sodium Sulphite and Alkali on Quinolono-pyrone,
trans-Hydroxyquinolyl acrylic Acids.*

These acids were obtained by the action of sodium sulphite and strong potassium hydroxide solution used successively. The following was the general procedure:—The quinolino-pyrone (4 g.) was treated with an aqueous solution of sodium sulphite (4 g. in 12 c.c. of water) and boiled until the solution gave no precipitate on neutralisation. This usually took about half an hour after which potassium hydroxide (5 g.) was added and the boiling continued for nearly an hour. On cooling the solution, crystals of the sodium salt of the *trans*-acrylic acid were slowly deposited. These were dissolved in water and the filtered solution carefully neutralised, when the free acid was obtained as a pale yellow flocculent precipitate which was collected and washed. It was found to be insoluble in all the common neutral solvents and was therefore purified by dissolving in dilute sodium carbonate solution in the cold and, after filtration, reprecipitating with dilute acids. It was boiled with absolute alcohol which removed the last traces of impurities and left the acid as a fine powder.

trans-6-Hydroxyquinolyl-5- β -acrylic acid prepared as above from quinolino-6:5- α -pyrone is a white powder, m.p. 220° (decomp). (Found: N, 6.7. C₁₁H₉O₃N requires N, 6.5 per cent.).

The acid dissolved readily in cold dilute hydrochloric acid and caustic soda yielding non-fluorescent yellow solutions from which on concentration the *hydrochloride* and the *sodium salt* separated as colourless and light yellow crystals respectively. It forms a bright yellow *silver* salt, a green *copper* salt, a buff coloured *ferric* salt, a yellow *nickel* salt and a brown *lead* salt. The silver salt was obtained by the method already given. It was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and then with alcohol, dried on a porous tile in a vacuum desiccator and analysed. (Found: Ag, 50.1. C₁₁H₇O₃NaAg₂ requires Ag, 50.4 per cent.).

Conversion of 6-Hydroxyquinolyl-5- β -acrylic Acid into Quinolono-pyrone.

The acid (0.5 g.) was treated with concentrated sulphuric acid (5 c.c.) and the solution heated in a boiling water-bath for an hour. It was then poured into cold water, filtered and the clear solution

treated with a slight excess of ammonia when quinolino-6:5- α -pyrone crystallised as fine, colourless needles, m. p. 232°.

Ethyl trans-6-Hydroxyquinolyl-5- β -acrylate.

The acid was made into a thin paste with absolute alcohol. When dry hydrogen chloride gas was passed into the mixture, a clear solution was obtained which was boiled under reflux for 8 hours and cooled: colourless needles of the sparingly soluble ester hydrochloride were formed. The whole was poured into water and the acid was neutralised by sodium bicarbonate. The precipitated ester, when crystallised from dilute alcohol, appeared as tufts of colourless needles, m. p. 198-199° (with vigorous decomposition). (Found: N, 5.7. $C_{14}H_{13}O_3N$ requires N, 5.8 per cent.).

The solid product of decomposition melted at 230-231°; it was extracted with a little boiling alcohol and the crystallised product was identified with quinolino-6:5- α -pyrone by a mixed melting point determination.

In order to identify the other products of decomposition, the ester (4 g.) was distilled in a test tube immersed in an oil-bath kept at 200°, and the volatile product which was absorbed in a little cold water was identified as ethyl alcohol by the iodoform test.

Methyl trans-6-Hydroxyquinolyl-5- β -acrylate was obtained by saturating a methyl alcoholic solution of the hydroxyquinolyl-acrylic acid with hydrogen chloride. Crystallisation from 50 per cent. alcohol gave colourless needles, m. p. 202° (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.1. $C_{13}H_{11}O_3N$ requires N, 6.1 per cent.).

The solid product of decomposition had m. p. 232°.

*Decomposition of trans-6-Hydroxyquinolyl-5- β -acrylic Acid
into 6-Hydroxyquinolyl-5- β -ethylene.*

The *trans*-acid (2 g.) was heated in a 50 c.c. distilling flask in an oil-bath under a pressure of 40 mm. The decomposition commenced at 170° and became fairly energetic at 190-200°; the acid slowly turned grey and colourless glistening needles sublimed. The temperature of the bath was finally raised to 225° when the whole mass quietly melted to a light brown liquid. The complete operation lasted about 2 hours, at the end of which the product was cooled, washed with a little alcohol and crystallised from a mixture

of pyridine and alcohol with the addition of a little animal charcoal to remove colour. Colourless prisms were obtained ; m.p. 256-257°, the yield being 60 per cent. of the theory. (Found: N, 8.4. $C_{11}H_{10}ON$ requires N, 8.2 per cent.).

The compound imparts a pink colour to ferric chloride solution; it is insoluble in a aqueous sodium carbonate or ammonia, but dissolves readily in aqueous sodium hydroxide yielding an almost colourless solution from which the sparingly soluble *sodium salt* quickly separates. It dissolves in dilute acids to form light green solutions. The sulphate is freely soluble whereas the hydrochloride and the nitrate are sparingly soluble and crystallise as shining colourless plates. Platinic chloride, mercuric chloride and potassium dichromate yield only amorphous precipitates. The pure dry *hydrochloride* was analysed. (Found: Cl, 16.9. $C_{11}H_{10}ONCl$ requires Cl, 17.1 per cent.).

trans-2-Methyl-6-hydroxyquinolyl-5- β -acrylic Acid.

This was prepared from 2-methyl-quinolino-6:5-*a*-pyrone by successive treatment with sodium sulphite and caustic potash. When purified by solution in sodium carbonate and reprecipitation and final boiling with alcohol, it forms a light yellow powder, m.p. 193° (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.3 $C_{11}H_{12}NO_3$ requires N, 6.1 per cent.).

The salts of the acid and its behaviour with concentrated sulphuric acid are similar to those of 6-hydroxy-quinolyl-5-acrylic acid. From its solution in concentrated hydrochloric acid light yellow rhombic plates of the *hydrochloride* were obtained. The deep yellow *silver salt* was prepared by the method already given. (Found: Ag, 48.9. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3NAg$, requires Ag, 48.7 per cent.).

The *ethyl ester* of this acid, obtained in the usual way, crystallised from alcohol as colourless, sharp needles, m.p. 146° (decomp.). (Found: N, 5.6. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3N$ requires N, 5.5 per cent.).

The product of decomposition when crystallised from alcohol, was identified with 2-methylquinolino-6:5-*a*-pyrone, m.p. 219-220°.

2-Methyl-6-hydroxyquinolyl-5- β -ethylene.

The decomposition of 2-methyl-6-hydroxyquinolyl-5- β -acrylic acid was effected in the same way as before. There was perceptible decomposition even at 150°; the temperature was slowly raised to 200° when the whole appeared as a light brown glassy mass. The

product was converted into the sparingly soluble hydrochloride and the crystals filtered and decomposed with ammonia. The free base separated from boiling alcohol in small colourless prisms, m. p. 241-242°. (Found: N, 7.7. $C_{11}H_{11}ON$ requires N, 7.6 per cent.).

It resembles the parent substance in all its properties and forms a sparingly soluble sodium salt and a hydrochloride and nitrate which readily crystallise from moderately concentrated solutions. The *hydrochloride* was analysed. (Found: Cl, 15.9. $C_{11}H_{11}ONCl$ requires Cl, 16.0 per cent.).

trans-8-Methyl-6-hydroxyquinolyl-5-β-acrylic Acid.

This was obtained in the usual manner from 8-methyl-quinolino-6:5-*a*-pyrone, and purified by conversion into the sparingly soluble hydrochloride which separated, even from dilute solutions, as colourless flat needles, m.p. 235° (decomp.). The free acid was liberated by neutralising the hot aqueous solution of the hydrochloride with ammonia. It crystallised from boiling alcohol, in which it dissolved rather sparingly, as yellow hexagonal plates, m.p. 195° (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.2. $C_{13}H_{11}NO_3$ requires N, 6.1 per cent.). The *silver salt* was obtained as a deep orange precipitate. (Found: Ag, 49.0. $C_{13}H_9O_3NaAg$ requires Ag, 48.7 per cent.).

The *ethyl ester* crystallises from dilute alcohol as colourless needles melting at 165-166° with loss of alcohol and the formation of 8-methyl-quinolino-6:5-*a*-pyrone. (Found: N, 5.4. $C_{15}H_{13}O_3N$ requires N, 5.5 per cent.).

8-Methyl-6-hydroxyquinolyl-5-β-ethylene.

The decomposition of 8-methyl-6-hydroxyquinolyl-5-β-acrylic acid was effected under a pressure of 50-60 mm. between 170° and 205°. The grey coloured product was washed with cold alcohol in order to remove impurities and finally crystallised from pyridine when it appeared as colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 244-245°. (Found: N, 7.8. $C_{11}H_{11}ON$ requires N, 7.6 per cent.). The compound is sparingly soluble in ether, chloroform and benzene. It imparts a pink colour to ferric chloride solution and forms a sodium salt and a hydrochloride which are sparingly soluble and crystalline. The *hydrochloride* was analysed. (Found: Cl, 16.2. $C_{11}H_{11}ONCl$ requires Cl, 16.0 per cent.).